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FLOATING MICROSPHERE: APPROACH IN MICROPARTICULATE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Prasad S. Galande, Pramodkumar J. Shirote, Roshan S. Ghorapde, Nikhil S. Dhumal

Department of Pharmaceutics, Arvind Gavali College of Pharmacy Jaitapur, Satara 415004, Maharashtra, India.

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ABSTRACT

The non-effervescent, gastro-retentive drug delivery technology known as floating microspheres (hollow microspheres). They are free-flowing powders between 1 and 1000 micrometres in size, made of proteins or artificial polymers. The goal of the floating microsphere is to increase stomach retention time. Low-density systems with enough buoyancy to float over gastric contents and stay in the stomach for a long time are referred to as gastro-retentive floating microspheres. In addition to tablets, capsules, and pills, there are also laminated films, floating microspheres, granules, and powders that are accessible as gastro-retentive dosage forms. Since dose frequency is reduced, the main advantage of floating microspheres is improved patient compliance. Spray drying, solvent evaporation, ionotropic gelation, single emulsion, double emulsion, phase separation coacervation, and solvent diffusion are some of the numerous methods used to prepare floating microspheres. This review discusses preparation techniques, characterization benefits, the mechanism by which pharmaceuticals are released from floating microspheres, a list of drugs, a list of uses, and a list of polymers.

Corresponding author

Mr. Prasad S. Galande.

Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics,

Arvind Gavali College of Pharmacy Jaitapur, Satara 415004, Maharashtra, India.

Prasadgalande17@gmail.com

07720949058

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INTRODUCTION

Current developments in new drug delivery systems aim to improve the security and the effectiveness of therapeutic molecular by creating an easy-to-administer dosage form. Using a non-effervescent method, floating microspheres are gastro-retentive drug delivery methods. Hollow microspheres, also known as floating microspheres, micro balloons, or floating microparticles. Floating microspheres are essentially spherical, empty particles without a core. These particles are between 1 to 1000 μm in size and are free-flowing. Hydrodynamically balanced systems (HBS) or floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) can float in the stomach for a long time without slowing down the rate at which the stomach empties because they have a lower bulk density than gastric fluids. The floating microspheres not only prolong the time of gastric retention but also regulate the stomach's volume by keeping the delivery system in a stable location and effectively delivering the medication.^[1-5]

Polymers used in floating microspheres^[6-7]

Hydrophilic polymer

These include cellulose derivatives such as HPMC and DEAE cellulose as well as egg albumin, gelatin, agar, starch, and chitosan.

Hydrophobic polymer

These include PMMA, acrylic acid esters, ethyl cellulose, and polylactic acid.

Biodegradable polymer

These compounds also slowly disappear from the administration site, but they do so as a result of a chemical process called hydrolysis.

Example: There are various generic classes, including the polyanhydrides and polyorthoesters, as well as polylactic acid (PLA), polyglycolic acid (PGA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and others.

Non - biodegradable hydrophobic polymer

These substances are eliminated or extracted intact from the administration site and remain inert in their environment of use.

Example: Polyethylene vinyl acetate (EVA), Polydimethyl siloxane (PDS), Polyether urethane (PEU), Ethyl cellulose (EC), Cellulose acetate (CA), Polyethylene (PE) and Polyvinyl chloride (PVC), Acrycoat, Eudragit S etc.

Hydrogels

When in contact with water, these polymers swell but do not dissolve. Hydrogels function similarly to hydrophobic polymers in that they are non-toxic, easily removed from the administration site, and act as a rate-limiting barrier to the transportation and release of medications.

Example: Polyacrylamide, crosslinked polyvinyl alcohol, crosslinked polyvinyl pyrrolidone, polyhydroxy ethyl methyl acrylate, etc.

Soluble polymer

These uncross-linked polymers with a moderate molecular weight (less than 75,000 daltons) dissolve in water. With an increase in molecular weight, the rate of dissolution decreases. These materials can be combined with hydrophobic polymers or used alone to create devices that gradually decline with time.

Example: Methacrylic acid and acrylic acid methyl ester copolymers (Eudragit L), polyethylene glycol (PEG), uncrosslinked poly vinyl alcohol or poly vinyl pyrrolidone, hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose (Methocel), etc.

Advantages^[8-14]

1. Improved bioavailability
2. Improvements in first-pass biotransformation
3. decreased variations in medication concentration
4. Site-specific medication delivery
5. Increased receptor activation selectivity
6. Reduces the body's natural defence mechanisms, increasing medication effectiveness.
7. The buoyancy of floating microspheres lengthens the period of gastric retention.
8. A drug with a brief half-life may provide therapeutic benefits with increased efficiency.
9. It can be accomplished by giving the medicine a controlled release more than a long period of time.
10. Site-specific medication delivery to the stomach is possible.
11. less variability between and among subjects.
12. Drug concentration fluctuations are kept to a minimum. As a result, undesirable effects that depend on concentration can be diminished.
13. Gastrointestinal diseases, including gastro-oesophageal reflux disease, are treated.

Disadvantages^[8, 9, 10, 15-18]

1. For these systems to float and work correctly during drug administration, the stomach must contain a lot of fluid.
2. Incompatible with medications that have GIT solubility or stability issues.
3. Medications that irritate the stomach mucosa are also inappropriate.
4. A floating drug delivery system should not be designed to administer medications that irritate or damage the stomach mucosa.
5. Due to its all-or-nothing emptying procedure, there is a high degree of fluctuation in gastric emptying time.
6. It might not be a good idea to use pharmaceuticals like nifedipine, which is well absorbed throughout the GIT and goes through first-pass metabolism.
7. These dosage delivery techniques for those medications, which circulate in the gastrointestinal tract after absorption, are not preferable to the traditional dosage forms.
8. FMs are not appropriate for medications that have stability issues in the stomach's acidic environment.

Mechanism of floating microspheres^[19-21]

The polysaccharides and polymers used to manufacture floating microspheres hydrate and create a colloidal gel barrier when they come into contact with gastric fluid. The barrier made of colloidal gel controls the rate at which fluid enters the floating microsphere, which has an impact on the medication release rate. The surrounding hydrocolloid layer is kept moist when the external surface of the microspheres dissolves, maintaining the hydrocolloid layer. The expanded polymers have trapped the air, lowering the density of the microspheres and enabling them to float above the gastric fluid. The least amount of stomach fluid must be present for buoyancy to be at its best.

Fig no. 1: Mechanism of floating microspheres.

Mechanism of drug release of floating microspheres**Diffusion:**

Diffusion of the drugs began when gastric fluid entered the microspheres' interior, where it was then dissolved and progressively released into the external media via a diffusion mechanism.^[22]

Erosion:

Some of the coverings that will be used to prepare the microspheres may gradually degrade over time, releasing the medication particle.^[23]

Osmosis:

When water enters the delivery system in a proper condition, osmotic pressure can be generated. Through the coating, this osmotic pressure forces the medication into the external medium.^[24]

Classification of floating drug delivery system

Two very different technologies, non-effervescent and effervescent systems, have been used in the creation of FDDS based on the mechanism of buoyancy:

1. Non-Effervescent FDDS.
2. Effervescent FDDS.

Non-Effervescent FDDS.

The FDDS in this class are typically made from hydrocolloids of the cellulose type that gel or swell readily, from polysaccharides, or from matrix-forming polymers like polyacrylate, polycarbonate, polystyrene, and polymethacrylate. Within the gel structure, the diffusing solvent creates a "receding boundary" as the drug in the dosage form dissolves inside and diffuses out. The different variations of this system include the following:^[25-26]

- Single Layer Floating Tablets
- Bi-layer Floating Tablet
- Alginate Beads
- Hollow Microspheres

Single Layer Floating Tablets

They are created by thoroughly blending the medication with a hydrocolloid, which, when in contact with stomach fluid, forms a gel and retains a bulk density below unity.

Bi-layer Floating Tablet

The immediate-release layer of a bi-layer tablet eliminates the first dose from the body, as gastric juices are absorbed by the sustained-release layer, a colloidal gel barrier that is impervious to gastric juices forms on its surface. These layers together maintain a bi-layer tablet's buoyancy in the stomach by maintaining a bulk density that is less than unity.

Alginate Beads

Calcium alginate precipitates and forms a porous system that can withstand a floating force for more than 12 hours when sodium alginate solution is added to a calcium chloride aqueous solution, producing spherical beads with an approximate diameter of 2.5 mm.

Hollow Microsphere

A medication was placed within the hollow microspheres (micro balloons) that were made using a unique emulsion-solvent diffusion process. For more than 12 hours in vitro, the microballoons floated continuously over the surfactant-containing acidic dissolution medium.^[27]

Effervescent FDDS.

The buoyant delivery method made use of either matrices with chambers of liquid that gasify at body temperature or matrices made of effervescent chemicals like sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, or tartaric acid with swellable polymers like Methocel or polysaccharides (like chitosan). There are two further categories for these effervescent systems.^[28]

- I. Gas Generating systems
- II. Volatile Liquid/Vacuum Containing Systems.

Gas Generating systems

Intra Gastric Single Layer Floating Tablets or Hydro dynamically Balanced System (HBS):

These are created by thoroughly combining the drug and CO₂ generators in the matrix tablet. The floating mechanism releases the medicine at the proper rate, and after it has been released entirely, the remaining system is ejected from the stomach. The GRT increases as a result, and the variations in plasma drug concentration are better controlled.

Intra Gastric Bi-layer Floating Tablets:

These are also compressed tablet and containing two layers i.e.,

- i. Immediate release layer and
- ii. Sustained release layer.

Volatile Liquid/Vacuum Containing Systems.

- 1) Intra-gastric Floating Gastrointestinal Drug Delivery System
- 2) Inflatable Gastrointestinal Delivery Systems
- 3) Intra-gastric Osmotically Controlled Drug Delivery System

Intra-gastric Floating Gastrointestinal Drug Delivery System

The flotation chamber, which may be a vacuum, be filled with air, or be filled with a safe gas, is what makes these devices float in the stomach. Inside a microporous chamber is the drug reservoir.

Inflatable Gastrointestinal Delivery Systems

In these devices, liquid ether is heated to body temperature in an inflatable chamber, where it gasifies and expands inside the stomach.

Intra-gastric Osmotically Controlled Drug Delivery System

It consists of an osmotic pressure-controlled medication delivery device, an inflatable floating support, and a biodegradable capsule. The drug reservoir compartment and the osmotically active compartment of the osmotic pressure-controlled drug delivery system are each divided into two parts.^[29-30]

Methods of preparations

Fig no. 2: Methods of preparations.

Spray drying

For the spray drying process, the polymer must first be dissolved in an appropriate volatile organic solvent. After that, high-speed homogenization is used to disperse the drug's solid form within the polymer solution. After that, a stream of hot air atomizes the dispersion. Small droplets or a fine mist are created during the atomization process, and the solvent rapidly evaporates from these droplets or mists to form microspheres that range in size from 1 to 100 micrometer.^[31]

Solvent evaporation

In the liquid production vehicle phase, the solvent evaporation process is carried out. The liquid production vehicle phase and the volatile solvent that is used to disseminate the microcapsule coating are incompatible. In the coated polymer solution, a core component that will be microencapsulated is dissolved or distributed. To create the proper-sized microcapsule, the core material combination is agitatedly disseminated in the liquid manufacturing vehicle phase.^[32]

Ionic gelation method

In this procedure, purified water was mixed with a cross-linking agent, polymer, and copolymer to create a homogeneous polymer mixture. To create a homogeneous dispersion, the medication was added to the polymer dispersion and vigorously swirled on a magnetic stirrer. In order to create the gelation medium, calcium chloride was dissolved in 2% glacial acetic acid. Using a syringe needle, the homogeneous alginate solution was extruded into the gelation medium. The microsphere was then collected, cleaned twice with distilled water, and 24 hours at room temperature are given for drying.^[33]

Fig no. 3: Ionic gelation method.

Single emulsion technique

By using a single emulsion technique, this technology creates microparticle carriers for natural polymers, such as proteins and carbohydrates. After being dissolved or dispersed in an aqueous medium with the help of a cross-linking agent, the natural polymers are disseminated in a non-aqueous medium, such as oil.^[34]

Double emulsion technique

The best medications for this approach are those that are water-soluble, like proteins and peptides. An aqueous protein solution is used to dissolve an emulsifier that contains drugs. This solution is then mixed with the lipophilic organic phase, which serves as a dispersed phase, to create a primary o/w emulsion. To form the double emulsion, the main emulsion is homogenised by the addition of an aqueous polyvinyl alcohol solution. Microspheres are created as the polyvinyl alcohol solution evaporates.^[35]

Phase separation coacervation technique

The theory behind it is that altering the solubility of the polymer in the organic phase will have an effect on how coacervates, a phase that is abundant in polymers, develop. After the drug particles have been disseminated in a polymer solution, the addition of an incompatible polymer causes the initial polymer to separate into phases and absorb the drug particles.^[36]

Emulsion solvent diffusion method

In this technique, a polymer and medication solution in ethanol and methylene chloride is mixed with an agitated aqueous polyvinyl alcohol solution. The methylene chloride droplets are surrounded by the polymer as the ethanol swiftly transforms into the outer aqueous phase. Internal cavities develop within the microparticles as a result of the entrapped methylene chloride's subsequent evaporation.^[37]

Evaluation of floating microspheres

Particle size

A microscopic approach was used to measure the particle size. This technique suspends floating Castor oil was used to prepare the microspheres. A momentary suspension put on a slide and examined with an optical microscope yielded roughly 600 particles, which were counted using a micrometre in the eyepiece. We counted every microsphere in a field.^[38-39]

Percentage yield

By dividing the product's actual weight by the total of all the non-volatile ingredients that will be used to create floating microspheres, the calculated floating microspheres are obtained. This process is explained by the formula below.

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \text{actual weight of microspheres} / \text{total weight of excipient and drug} \times 100^{[40]}$$

Entrapment efficiency

All floating microsphere batches will have an accurately measured amount of floating microspheres that have been crushed. In a volumetric flask with a capacity of 100 ml, after being dissolved in 5 ml of ethanol, the powdered microspheres will be diluted with 0.1 N HCL to the proper volume. Filter paper made by Whatmann was used. The sample will be examined by a UV spectrophotometer after filtration, and the absorbance will be measured in comparison to a blank of 0.1 N HCL. The calculation for the drug entrapment percentage is as follows:

$$\% \text{ drug entrapment} = \text{Calculated drug concentration} / \text{theoretical drug concentration} \times 100^{[41]}$$

Bulk density

It refers to the blend mass to bulk volume ratio. It was calculated by filling a measuring cylinder with powder and counting the amount of space the powder occupied.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{weight of powder} / \text{bulk volume}^{[42]}$$

Tapped density

It is the proportion of blend mass to volume that has been tapped. The volume of powder occupied after 100 standard taps was measured using a digital tap densitometer.

$$\text{Tapped density} = \text{weight of powder} / \text{tapped volume}^{[43]}$$

Hausners ratio

A measurement of a powder's ability to be compressed is the Hausner's ratio. By utilising the formula, it is determined.

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = (\text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density}) \times 100$$

A powder's flowability can often be determined by looking at the Hausner's ratio. A Hausner's ratio higher than 1.25 is regarded as a sign of poor flowability.^[44]

Angle of repose

The angle of repose of the microspheres was calculated using the funnel method. The microspheres were poured using a funnel that could be raised vertically to create the tallest cone possible.

A calculation was made of the heap's radius and the angle of repose.

$$\tan \theta = h/r^{[45]}$$

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Using an electron microscope, examine the beads' surface morphology and shape. Beads were fixed on the SEM sample stub using double-sided adhesive tape, and under low pressure (0.001 mm of Hg), a 200-nm-thick gold layer was applied to the beads. We observed the beads at a 10KV accelerating voltage.^[47]

In vitro Buoyancy

A USP dissolving test apparatus II was used to examine how microspheres floated, as described in USP I. The dispersing medium (900 ml of 0.1 N HCl) is covered with 50 mg of the microspheres, which are dispersed using 0.02% Tween 80 as a surfactant. The dissolution medium was kept at 37°C while being stirred by a paddle that rotated at 100 rpm. After 12 hours, the floating and settled microspheres were separately collected. The microspheres were filtered, dried, and weighed. The following equation was used to determine the percentage of floating microspheres:

$$\text{Percentage Buoyancy} = W_f / W_f + W_s$$

Where, W_f and W_s are the masses of the floating and settled microparticles.^[44]

X-Ray diffraction technique (XRD) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

It is important to determine the drug's physical state in multiple unit systems. During the process, there is a chance that the drug's crystallinity will change, and these changes may have an impact on the drug's release characteristics. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) are two methods that can be used to examine the crystallinity of a drug.^[46]

In vitro drug release studies

Using a USP dissolving device type I or type II, the drug release rate from hollow floating microspheres is assessed at 37 0.5 °C. 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl dissolution medium are used in the dissolution test, which is run for the required amount of time at 100 rpm. At the proper intervals, a certain volume of aliquots is removed and replaced with an equivalent volume of new dissolving liquid to maintain the volume of the dissolution medium constant. Whatman filter paper is used to filter the sample solutions, and a UV spectrophotometer is used to analyse the results.^[40,47]

Applications of floating microspheres

Fig no. 4: Applications of floating microspheres.

Sustained drug delivery

Since these systems can stay in the stomach for a long time, the medicine can be delivered gradually. With these approaches, the issue of a brief gastric residence period that arises with an oral CR formulation can be resolved. Due to their bulk density of 1, they can float on the contents of the stomach. Because of their size, these systems cannot fit through the pyloric aperture, which is relatively large.^[10]

Site specific drug delivery

For drugs like riboflavin and furosemide, which are largely absorbed through the stomach or proximal small intestine, these systems are extremely helpful. Floating microspheres can significantly enhance the pharmacotherapy of the stomach through local drug release, resulting in high drug concentrations at the gastric mucosa, eradicating *Helicobacter pylori* from the stomach's submucosal tissue, and allowing the treatment of stomach and duodenal ulcers, gastritis, and oesophagitis.^[48]

Absorption enhancement

Floating microspheres are particularly good at delivering insoluble and sparingly soluble drugs. It is well known that as a medication's solubility diminishes, less time is available for drug dissolution. As a result, transit time becomes a significant factor determining drug absorption. Hollow microspheres may prevent the possibility that solubility may become the rate-limiting step in release for weakly basic medications that are poorly soluble at an alkaline pH by limiting such pharmaceuticals to the stomach. The gastric release is advantageous for medications that are efficiently absorbed by the stomach, such as verapamil hydrochloride. The gastro-retentive floating microspheres will change how the active ingredient is absorbed, enhancing its bioavailability.^[49]

As carriers

Drugs with so-called "absorption windows," such as antiviral, antifungal, and antibiotic agents (sulphonamides, quinolones, penicillins, cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, and tetracyclines), which can only be absorbed from very specific sites of the GI mucosa, can be transported by floating multiparticulates. Pharmacokinetic benefits and future potential: Floating dosage forms offer a variety of potential benefits as sustained release systems, as is clear from a number of recent publications. It is possible to deliver medications effectively, maximising absorption and increasing absolute bioavailabilities, for medicines with low bioavailability since only the upper GI tract can absorb them.^[50]

Examples of drugs involved in floating microspheres^[51]

Table no.1: Examples of drugs involved in floating microspheres.

Drug	Category	Method of preparations	Uses	Brand name
Nateglinide	Antidiabetic	Emulsion solvent evaporation method	Type 2 Diabetes	Starlix
Rabeprazole sodium	Antiulcer	Emulsion solvent evaporation method	Gastro esophageal reflux disease	Aciphex
Esomeprazole	Antiulcer	Solvent evaporation method	Gastrointestinal ulcer	Nexium
Lamivudine	antiretroviral	Solvent evaporation method	Human immunodeficiency virus	Epivir
Captopril	ACE Inhibitors	Solvent evaporation	Hypertension	Catopil

CONCLUSION

A successful method for improving the bioavailability and regulated administration of different medicinal drugs is the use of floating microspheres. Floating microspheres as gastro-retentive dosage forms provide a huge influence on health care by carefully controlling the target drug's release rate to a specific region. This review article mainly describes mechanism of floating microspheres, the method of preparation, evaluation parameter and application of floating microspheres. This review also focuses on the many drug types, their categories, preparation techniques, and brand names.

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